

Asymptotic view of oscillations of red giant stars

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Abstract

Since the pioneering works by Vandakurov (1967), Shibahashi (1979) and Tassoul (1980), asymptotic analysis has been of fundamental use in the study of stellar oscillations. This is a theoretical framework to understand the physics of the oscillations under the assumption that the wavelength of the constituent waves are much shorter than the scale height of the background structure. The recent detection of solar-like oscillations in red giant stars provides another case for the application of the framework. In this paper, it is described how the asymptotic analysis can be extended to the case of the red giant oscillations in order to understand their unique characteristics and the internal structure of the stars. The analysis turns out to be useful to extract detailed information from the complicated frequency spectra, which have been obtained by the recent space missions.

1 Introduction

Seismology of red giant stars is one of the most successful branches in asteroseismology in these days. This is mainly thanks to the secure detection of faint solar-like (i.e. stochastically excited) oscillations in a vast number of red giants by space missions such as CoRoT and *Kepler*, which have conducted long-term continuous photometric observations of a huge number of stars in particular regions of the sky with high precision. From a physical point of view, the most remarkable property of the red-giant oscillations is that modes of a special class, which are called the mixed modes, are observed. The modes consist of gravity waves in the dense core, which are restored by the buoyancy force, and acoustic waves in the extended envelope, whose restoring force is the pressure gradient. The characteristics of the modes therefore reflect the physical conditions of both the core and envelope of the stars. This is in sharp contrast to the case of the main-sequence solar-like oscillators, including the Sun itself, in which only modes composed of acoustic waves (p modes) have been observed. Since the p modes are trapped only in the envelope, it is difficult to get information about the central part of those stars by seismology.

While the mixed modes are very useful to probe the entire structure of the stars, their frequency spectrum is more complicated than that of the main-sequence oscillators. When the wavelength of the constituent waves in the radial direction is much shorter than the scale height of the background structure, the frequency spectrum of p modes is primarily characterized by constant frequency spacing, while that of g modes, which are composed of only gravity waves, is mainly explained by constant period spacing. Roughly speaking, the spectrum of the mixed modes shows a mixture of these two different patterns.

In order to provide a theoretical framework to understand such complicated frequency structure of the mixed modes, asymptotic analysis has been developed under the assumption of the short wavelength, which greatly simplifies the analytical treatment of the problem. The two standard references for the asymptotic theory of the mixed modes are Shibahashi (1979) and Tassoul (1980). While an earlier work about the asymptotic theory of the stellar oscillation by Vandakurov (1967) has analysed only the p and g modes, the two papers also discuss the mixed modes. In fact, the mixed modes and their related phenomenon, avoided crossing, were recognized by the stellar oscillation community only a few

years before the two papers [e.g. Osaki (1975) and Aizenman *et al.* (1977)].

Given that the original asymptotic theory of the mixed modes was developed a few decades before the detection of the solar-like oscillations in red giants, it is not surprising that some problems of the theory have been identified in the analysis of the recent observations, and that new efforts have been made to resolve these problems. In this paper, the latest development of the asymptotic analysis of the solar-like oscillations in red giants is reviewed with some discussions about related topics.

2 Revision of the asymptotic theory of the mixed modes

Two problems are addressed in the conventional asymptotic analyses of the mixed modes that have been developed by Shibahashi (1979) and Tassoul (1980). The solutions to both of them are given by Takata (2016a), whose results are summarized.

2.1 Problem 1: effects of the perturbation to the gravitational field on dipolar modes

An important assumption of the conventional asymptotic analyses is neglect of the perturbation to the gravitational potential, which is called the Cowling approximation (Cowling, 1941). The merit of this treatment is to reduce the order of the ordinary differential equation that governs the radial part of the oscillation equation from four to two. It is obvious that the asymptotic analysis of the fourth-order equation is much more difficult than that of the second-order equation. Although the approximation is generally good for high-order (i.e. short-wavelength) modes, this is not the case for the behaviour of dipolar modes near the centre. The reason is that, unlike in the other modes, the mass elements at the centre of the stars, where the density is highest, are displaced in the course of the oscillations in the dipolar modes, which induces non-negligible contribution to the gravitational field in the vicinity. In fact, it is this type of eigenmodes that plays the most important role in red-giant seismology. The other types are not suitable to probe the core structure, because the radial (spherically symmetric) modes cannot in principle have the gravity-wave component, while the higher-degree modes (those with more complicated horizontal structure) with sufficient amplitude in the core are hard to be detected at the

surface.

A way to overcome this trouble is to adopt the formulation of the oscillation equations specific to the dipolar oscillation that is derived in Takata (2006). The formulation fully takes account of the perturbation to the gravitational potential, but still keeps the order of the differential equation at two. In this case, the order of the equation can be reduced from four to two by using the exact relation of momentum conservation that is specific to the dipolar oscillation (Takata, 2005), and choosing the dependent variable carefully.

The derived second-order system of differential equations actually has the same form as that in the case of the Cowling approximation. The differences are still found in the following points:

1. The dependent variables are the radial and horizontal components of the reduced displacement vector, ζ , which is defined by

$$\zeta \equiv \xi - r_g . \quad (1)$$

Here, ξ and r_g are the displacement vector of mass elements at a given position and the displacement of the centre of mass of the concentric mass that is contained inside the radius of the position, respectively.

2. The two characteristics frequencies of the stellar oscillation, the Lamb frequency, L_1 , and Brunt–Väisälä frequency, N , are replaced with their modified versions,

$$\hat{L}_1 = L_1 \left(1 - \frac{\rho}{\rho_{av}} \right) \quad (2)$$

and

$$\hat{N} = N \left(1 - \frac{\rho}{\rho_{av}} \right)^{-1} , \quad (3)$$

respectively, where ρ and ρ_{av} are the density at a given position and the average density of the concentric mass inside the radius of the position, respectively. While the difference between the modified and original frequencies is generally very small in the outside of the central region of red giants, the impact of the modification is so strong near the centre that the constituent waves of the modes have significantly different phase lags in the reflection near the centre. In fact, the modified Lamb (Brunt–Väisälä) frequency goes to zero (infinity) at the centre, whereas the original frequency tends to infinity (zero). Figures 1 and 2 show the characteristic frequencies of representative models of stars on the red giant branch (RGB). All of the evolutionary models in this paper are computed by the MESA stellar evolution code (Paxton *et al.*, 2011).

2.2 Problem 2: thin intermediate evanescent region

The main result of the conventional asymptotic analyses of the mixed modes is the eigenfrequency condition, which is derived as follows: the stationary-wave solutions of the oscillation equations are constructed for the gravity-wave oscillations in the core and the acoustic-wave oscillations in the envelope; the two solutions are then matched with each other in the intermediate region between the core and the envelope, where the oscillations are evanescent. In this process, it is essential to assume that the interaction between the oscillations in the core and the envelope is so weak that the solution in each propagative region can be extrapolated to the evanescent region separately before the matching. The

Figure 1: Profiles of the characteristic frequencies of the dipolar stellar oscillation for an evolutionary model of a star on the red giant branch with the mass of $M = 1.2 M_\odot$, the radius of $R = 3.84 R_\odot$ and the large frequency separation of $\Delta\nu = 19.7 \mu\text{Hz}$. Plotted are the Lamb and Brunt–Väisälä frequencies and their modified versions, which are defined by equations (2) and (3), respectively. The frequencies are normalized by $\sqrt{GM/R^3}$, where G is the gravitational constant. The thick horizontal band represents a rough idea of the expected frequency range of observed modes. The horizontal coordinate u in the lower axis is a radial function defined by integrating $-gc^{-2}(1 - \rho/\rho_{av})^{-1}$ over radius r , where g and c are the local gravitational acceleration and the sound speed, respectively.

Figure 2: Same as figure 1, but for a more evolved model on the RGB with $M = 1.2 M_\odot$, $R = 8.10 R_\odot$ and $\Delta\nu = 6.3 \mu\text{Hz}$. One difference from the model in Figure 1 is that the outer boundary of the core propagative region at the (expected) observed frequencies is essentially fixed at the base of the convective zone, and hence is almost independent of the frequency.

assumed situation corresponds to the case where the intermediate evanescent region is very thick. (In this context, the thickness of the region is measured by the geometrical size divided by a typical e -folding distance of the eigenfunctions in the region.) While the assumption is supported by evolutionary stellar models at the late stage of the RGB (cf. Figure 2), the evanescent region is quite thin in the early stage of the RGB (cf. Figure 1) and in the helium core burning phase.

It is therefore necessary to take account of the interaction of the oscillations between the core and the envelope when the solutions are extrapolated. In fact, discarding the assumption of the thin evanescent region causes a substantially complicated mathematical problem in the asymptotic analysis. Generally speaking, a highlight of the asymptotic analysis is to solve turning-point problems, whose purpose is to relate solutions in evanescent regions to ones in propagative regions. If the intermediate evanescent region of red giants is thick enough, the task is accomplished by analyzing two approximate equations (Airy differential equations) separately, one of which is valid only near the boundary (turning point) between the core propagative region and the intermediate evanescent region, and the other of which is good only close to the boundary between the envelope propagative region and the intermediate evanescent region. On the other hand, when the two turning points are located closely to each other, another turning-point equation need to be solved alternatively to the two Airy equations to describe the two transitions of the solutions simultaneously, one from the evanescent region to the core, and the other from the evanescent region to the envelope.

The problem is even more complicated because it is not straightforward to derive the convenient form of the alternative equation, which can formally be written as

$$\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + F(x) y = 0. \quad (4)$$

Here, the dependent variable y means an oscillation variable, while the independent variable x is a function that specifies a radial point. The coefficient function F , which physically corresponds to the squared wavenumber of the oscillation in the propagative regions, changes for different choices of x and y . In fact, so far as y is not chosen carefully, F is essentially provided by

$$F(x) = Ax + \frac{B}{x - x_1}, \quad (5)$$

where A , B and x_1 are all constants different from 0. The positions of $x = 0$ and $x = x_1$ correspond to the two boundaries between the propagative and evanescent regions. The singular point at $x = x_1$ particularly makes the analytical treatment difficult because it generally causes singular (and hence unphysical) behaviour of y . This problem persists in any standard choices of the dependent variable, including the (reduced) radial displacement, the (reduced) horizontal displacement, the Lagrangian pressure perturbation and the Eulerian pressure perturbation.

As a solution to the problem, Takata (2016a) manages to replace the singular point with a zero point by adopting a complex variable, w , rather than a real variable as the dependent variable. The resultant equation, which is the key to the turning-point problem, can be approximated by the Weber differential equation,

$$\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + C(x^2 - x_0^2) w = 0, \quad (6)$$

in which C and x_0 are complex constants. Although the equation need to be analyzed in the complex domain because

not only the dependent variable but also the coefficient function is complex, it is still possible to obtain the analytic expressions of the asymptotic solutions.

2.3 Eigenfrequency condition

The eigenfrequency condition that is derived in Takata (2016a) is given by

$$\tan \Theta_p \cot \Theta_g = q, \quad (7)$$

in which Θ_p and Θ_g represent the phases of the oscillations, including their lags introduced at the boundaries, in the envelope and the core, respectively. The quantity q is called the coupling factor (or coefficient), which physically means the strength of the interaction of the oscillations between the core and the envelope. Although equation (7) is of the same form as the eigenfrequency condition given by Shibahashi (1979) and Tassoul (1980), the differences are found in the definitions of all of q , Θ_p and Θ_g . The definition of q is changed so that it can take any value between 0 and 1, whereas the conventional definition of Shibahashi (1979) and Tassoul (1980) indicates that q must be between 0 and $1/4$. This change in the range of q is essential in the interpretation of the observations because some red giants actually show the value of q over $1/4$ [e.g. Mosser *et al.* (2017b)]. Further discussion of this issue is given section 3. The phase of the envelope oscillation Θ_p has a term of the phase lag that is introduced at the inner turning point (of the envelope propagative region). While this term is fixed to $\pi/4$ in the conventional definition, it depends on q in the revised definition, so that it reflects the effect of the interaction of the oscillations between the two propagative regions. The phase lag is equal to $\pi/4$ in the limit of no interaction ($q = 0$), while it monotonically decreases as q is larger, and gets to $\pi/8$ in the limit of $q = 1$. In fact, the same term is found in Θ_g , which is induced by the reflection at the outer boundary of the core propagative region. Another change in Θ_g by $\pi/2$ is caused by the effect of the perturbation to the gravitational potential, which is discussed in section 2.1. Furthermore, the revised analysis takes account of the effect of the central singularity on the phase lag at the inner turning point of the core propagative region.

2.4 Interpretation of the period spacing and the gravity offset

Another point of the revised eigenfrequency condition is to give theoretical justification to an empirical expression of Θ_g by Mosser *et al.* (2012b), who propose the form,

$$\Theta_g = \pi \left(\frac{1}{\nu \Delta \Pi_1} - \varepsilon_g \right), \quad (8)$$

for better fit to the observed frequencies. Here, ν is the cyclic frequency of the oscillation, while the period spacing $\Delta \Pi_1$ and the gravity offset ε_g are frequency-independent parameters. Note that the first term in the parenthesis is much larger than the second term on the right-hand side of equation (8). On the other hand, the small term, ε_g , does not appear (explicitly) in the conventional asymptotic analyses, while $\Delta \Pi_1$ in equation (8) should be replaced by

$$\Delta \Pi_1^* = \frac{2\pi^2}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\int_{\text{core}} \frac{N}{r} dr \right)^{-1}, \quad (9)$$

in which the range of the integral is that of the core propagative region. There accordingly exist two problems in accepting equation (8) from a theoretical point of view. Firstly, it is not possible to naively identify $\Delta \Pi_1$ as $\Delta \Pi_1^*$ because the

Figure 3: Evolution of the gravity offset ε_g computed based on the revised asymptotic theory for evolutionary models with the mass of $1.2 M_\odot$. Note that the large frequency separation $\Delta\nu$ decreases along with the evolution.

range of the integral, and hence $\Delta\Pi_1^*$, depends on the frequency. Secondly, the physical origin of ε_g is not clear. In fact, there appear to be some confusions in the literature related to the first problem. Some people interpret $\Delta\Pi_1$ as the value of $\Delta\Pi_1^*$ at $\nu = \nu_{\max}$, the frequency of the maximum oscillation power of each star. Others calculate the integral over the entire radiative region.

The observed period spacing $\Delta\Pi_1$ can be interpreted as follows. The first step is to approximate $(\Delta\Pi_1^*)^{-1}$ by a linear function of ν as

$$(\Delta\Pi_1^*)^{-1} = H(\nu) \approx H_0(\nu), \quad (10)$$

in which H_0 is defined by

$$H_0(\nu) \equiv H(\nu_{\max}) + H'(\nu_{\max})(\nu - \nu_{\max}). \quad (11)$$

Note that $H_0(\nu)$ is just a truncated Taylor expansion of $H(\nu)$ at $\nu = \nu_{\max}$. It then follows

$$\frac{1}{\nu\Delta\Pi_1^*} \approx \frac{H_0(0)}{\nu} + H'(\nu_{\max}), \quad (12)$$

which means $\Delta\Pi_1$ can be identified as

$$(\Delta\Pi_1)^{-1} = H_0(0). \quad (13)$$

Namely, the observable parameter $(\Delta\Pi_1)^{-1}$ can be interpreted as the limiting value of the linear approximation of $(\Delta\Pi_1^*)^{-1}$ at $\nu = 0$.

Equation (12) also implies that ε_g can be (partially) explained by $-H'(\nu_{\max})$. It should be noted, however, that the phase lags at the both boundaries of the core propagative region, which are modified in the revised analysis, also contribute to ε_g . Hekker *et al.* (2018) and Mosser *et al.* (2018) have recently succeeded in measuring ε_g of a number of red giants observed by the *Kepler* spacecraft. Detailed comparison of these results with the revised asymptotic theory will hopefully provide new insights into the core structure of the red giants. As an initial trial, the values of ε_g are computed for evolutionary models with the mass of $1.2 M_\odot$ on the RGB based on the revised asymptotic analysis. The results are depicted in Figure 3. The computed results reasonably agree with the observations given by Mosser *et al.* (2018).

3 Progressive-wave picture of the mixed modes

While the asymptotic analysis developed in Takata (2016a) is mathematically elaborate and complicated, some aspects of the results can be obtained much more easily based on physical considerations. Takata (2016b) demonstrates that the eigenfrequency condition given by equation (7) can be obtained based on the progressive-wave picture of the mixed modes. The system is regarded as composed of three regions: two regions of the wave propagation (those in the core and the envelope), which are divided by a wall (the intermediate evanescent region). If a progressive wave is incident on the wall from the right in the envelope propagative region, it is split into two components, one reflected back to the right direction in the envelope region and the other transmitted to the core propagative region. This is nothing but a well-known topic in elementary wave physics, the partial reflection and transmission problem, or the tunnel effect in quantum mechanics. The key parameters of the problem are the phase lags of the wave components introduced at the reflection, and the coefficients of reflection (R) and transmission (T), which are the amplitudes of the reflected and transmitted components, respectively, normalized by that of the incident wave.

In order to discuss the mixed modes, it is necessary to consider another situation in which the incident wave comes from the left in the core propagative region. It may be called the adjoint problem, while the original problem is named the base problem. Because the system does not possess the mirror symmetry with respect to the wall, it is not obvious how the key parameters of the base problem are related to those of the adjoint problem. It can actually be shown that the reflection and transmission coefficients of the two problems are common under the following fundamental physical assumptions about the wave solutions of the system: (1) time-reversal symmetry, (2) time-shift symmetry, (3) principle of superposition and (4) energy conservation ($R^2 + T^2 = 1$). Based on these results, the mixed modes can be constructed by making a linear combination of the wave solutions of the base and adjoint problems, and applying proper boundary conditions (of no energy loss and gain) at the inner boundary of the core region and the outer boundary of the envelope region. The obtained eigenfrequency condition has certainly the same form as equation (7), with the identification of

$$q = \frac{1 - R}{1 + R}, \quad (14)$$

which explicitly provides the relation between the (common) reflection coefficient and the coupling factor. Equation (14) implies that q is changed from 0 to 1, as R is varied from 1 to 0. On the other hand, if the transmission coefficient satisfies $T \ll 1$, R can approximately be given by $R = \sqrt{1 - T^2} \approx 1 - T^2/2$, which can then be substituted into equation (14) to yield

$$q \approx \frac{T^2}{4}. \quad (15)$$

Equation (15) means that q cannot be larger than 1/4, which is realized when T is formally set to 1 (in spite of the assumption of $T \ll 1$). See Figure 4 for the comparison between the revised definition [equation (14)] and the approximation for small T given by equation (15). The case of small T corresponds to that of little interaction in the oscillations between the core and envelope, as is assumed in the conventional asymptotic analyses. Therefore, the formal upper limit on q of 1/4 in the conventional analyses is a consequence of the assumption of the weak interaction.

Figure 4: Profiles of the coupling factor q as functions of the reflection coefficient R .

Figure 5: Evolution of the coupling factor q . The asymptotic values computed for evolutionary models with the mass of $1.2 M_{\odot}$ are shown by the solid line, while the observed results for a sample of red giants in the *Kepler* field by Mosser *et al.* (2017b) are shown in the background.

According to the asymptotic theory, the reflection coefficient R , and hence the coupling factor q , is determined by the structure of the intermediate evanescent region, which is delimited by the (modified) Lamb and Brunt–Väisälä frequencies. The revised asymptotic formula for q has been applied to evolutionary models on the RGB with the mass of $1.2 M_{\odot}$. The computed values are compared in Figure 5 with those of *Kepler* red giants that are measured by Mosser *et al.* (2017b). The agreement between the theory and the observations may not look perfect, but is reasonable at least.

4 Asymptotic parameters of the depressed dipolar modes

As an example to show how useful the asymptotic theory is, the current situation of the problem of the depressed dipolar modes is reviewed.

It is known that a significant fraction of the red giants observed by *Kepler* have much lower amplitude of the dipolar modes than the majority of the stars (Mosser *et al.*, 2012a; García *et al.*, 2014). Because these stars are unexpected in the

standard picture of the solar-like oscillations of red giants, they have become an interesting topic of red-giant seismology.

Fuller *et al.* (2015) hypothesize the strong magnetic field in the core of these stars, which is supposed to be generated in the convective core during the main-sequence stage. [This idea itself is supported by Stello *et al.* (2016) who find that the mass of the stars with the depressed dipolar modes distributes in the range above $1.2 M_{\odot}$. This agrees with the range for which the core of the main-sequence stars is expected to be convective.] The acoustic waves that are constituents of the dipolar modes in the envelope are generated in the near-surface turbulent layers of the stars, and partially transmitted to the core as the gravity waves. Then, the core field scatters the incident waves from the envelope with dipolar structure to convert them to those with the complicated structure dominated by higher-degree components, which can hardly go back to the envelope because of the thick evanescent region between the core and the envelope. The net effect is thus the loss of energy of the dipolar modes in the core.

A prediction of this hypothesis (magnetic greenhouse effect) is that, if any component of the waves transmitted to the core from the envelope cannot come back at all to the envelope, the constructed modes are not the mixed modes because there is no interaction in the oscillations between the core and the envelope. In other words, the observed frequency structure should be close to that of the pure acoustic modes, which are found in the limiting case of the coupling factor of 0. Mosser *et al.* (2017a), however, find clear evidence that the depressed dipolar modes are mixed modes, so that the hypothesis is too crude as the answer to the problem at least in its original form.

Loi & Papaloizou (2017) also consider the strong magnetic field in the core, which is composed of both of the poloidal and toroidal components. As in the case of Fuller *et al.* (2015), the acoustic waves that are excited near the surface are partially transmitted to the core as the gravity waves. When the waves come to the core magnetic region, the spheroidal oscillations with the dipolar structure are supposed to induce the torsional oscillation that consist of Alfvén waves travelling along the field lines because of the toroidal magnetic component. For a given frequency of the incident oscillations, the induced Alfvén waves satisfy the condition for eigenmodes (Alfvén modes) at particular radii. Thus, the dipolar modes are resonantly coupled with the Alfvén modes in the magnetic region. The wavelength of the induced Alfvén modes is so short that they experience efficient magnetic damping, which is the origin of the depression of the dipolar modes.

One of the assumptions that Loi & Papaloizou (2017) make is that the core magnetic field little influences the spheroidal component of the oscillations, and affects almost only the toroidal component (to be damped). This means that the asymptotic parameters such as the period spacing and the coupling factor should not be different from those found in the stars with the standard (non-depressed) modes, which has actually been confirmed by Mosser *et al.* (2017a). However, Loi & Papaloizou (2017) assume in their particular model that the strength of the magnetic field is of the order of MG, the similar value adopted by Fuller *et al.* (2015), who regard that the spheroidal component of the dipolar structure is almost completely destroyed by the field (through the scattering process). It is therefore necessary to examine whether that size of the field in reality has little impact on the spheroidal oscillation or not. In fact, Loi & Papaloizou (2018) perform more detailed study of the model to show that the magnetic field that is strong enough to real-

ize the efficient damping through the resonant coupling with the Alfvén modes inevitably modifies the structure of the spheroidal oscillation substantially. This means that the original picture of Loi & Papaloizou (2017) cannot be supported.

It is in addition not possible to accept the alternative picture considered by Loi & Papaloizou (2018) that not only the toroidal component but also the spheroidal component is modified by the core magnetic field. In that case, it is expected that the period spacing is larger in the stars with the depressed dipolar modes than in those with the normal amplitude of the modes. This can be understood by the following argument. In order to observe any detectable effects on the oscillation modes, the core magnetic field should extend to the propagative region in the core. If the waves that originate from the envelope are incident on the magnetic region, part of them are reflected keeping their dipolar structure, and transmitted back to the envelope. It is this component that contributes to the construction of the dipolar mixed modes. Since the layers of the reflection are located outer than the inner turning point of the core propagative region (in the absence of the magnetic field), the effective size of the core propagative region is reduced by the magnetic field, which results in the increase of the period spacing of the constructed modes [cf. equation (9)]. Such increase is nevertheless not detected by Mosser *et al.* (2017a).

5 Concluding remarks

The massive and high-precision data from space missions such as CoRoT and *Kepler* have greatly advanced the observational side of asteroseismology. Above all, study of solar-like oscillations in red giants has become one of the most fruitful subjects in the field.

The asymptotic theory provides an indispensable framework to interpret the complicated frequency spectrum of the mixed modes of red giants. The original theory, which was developed by Shibahashi (1979) and Tassoul (1980), need to be revised to be applicable to the dipolar mixed modes. The revision, which was first proposed empirically to explain the observed frequencies (e.g. Mosser *et al.*, 2012b), has been justified by recent theoretical efforts (Takata, 2016a,b). Our understanding of the core structure of the red giants would be further improved by interpreting the observed mixed-mode parameters including the period spacing, the coupling factor and the gravity offset based on the revised asymptotic theory. In addition, the asymptotic parameters are also useful to study the origin of the depressed dipolar modes by checking whether the predicted values of the hypotheses that explain the phenomenon are consistent with the observed values or not.

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